

Comparison of double-star absolute astrometry (18 months)

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1. Introduction

After the previous message (DSWG.LO.002) I received a corrected file from Hans-Heinrich (dated 17 Febr). This report covers my comparison of that file with Staffan's data from 17 January. 21 stars had to be skipped in the FAST file and three in the NDAC file because of format overflow (numerical fields containing asterisks). Usually these solutions either had very large sigmas (> 999 mas) or unreasonable parallaxes and/or proper motions, so it's probably no loss. A total of 2634 stars could be read and were found in both files. For 761 of them there are also data from the NDAC 30 months sphere solution. The epoch for the comparison of positions is 1990.75.

For 30 of the systems it was necessary to interchange the primary/secondary in the NDAC data. The criterion used to select these systems was:

$$|\theta_F - \theta_N| > 165 \text{ deg} \quad \text{AND} \quad |\rho_F - \rho_N| < 50 \text{ mas} \quad \text{AND} \quad \Delta m_F + \Delta m_N < 0.5$$

where θ , ρ and Δm stand for the position angle, separation and magnitude difference.

2. System orientation

To begin with I applied the same rotation vectors in position and proper motion as found from the 18 months (iterated) sphere solutions, viz.:

$$(+15.568, +13.835, -11.414, +0.0676, -4.203, +5.049). \quad (1)$$

However, I soon found systematic differences in the positions and proper motions which indicated that this rotation was not completely correct. A direct solution of the rotation vectors (using the very robust L1 norm) gave:

$$(+15.155, +14.507, -12.744, -0.225, -1.312, +2.780). \quad (2)$$

As before, the FAST data were transformed to the NDAC system by application of this vector.

The difference between (1) and (2) is significant (it was also verified by making independent solutions for subsets of the stars) and amounts to about 2 mas in position and 4 mas/yr in proper motion. Thus, either the FAST or the NDAC double star data are not on exactly the same system as the respective sphere solution. Direct comparison with the sphere data indicates that it is the FAST system that has changed, although the scarcity of data does not allow a definite conclusion (only a few hundred stars could be used for this comparison).

3. Relative data

Many of the solutions disagree completely on the relative positions of the components, and it is probably not very useful to compare the absolute data for such systems. As a measure of the agreement in the relative astrometry I have used the quantity

$$\Delta(\text{rel}) = (\Delta x^2 + \Delta y^2)^{0.5} \quad (3)$$

with

$$\Delta x = \rho_N \sin \theta_N - \rho_F \sin \theta_F \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta y = \rho_N \cos \theta_N - \rho_F \cos \theta_F .$$

The distribution of $\Delta(\text{rel})$ shows some interesting features which are best seen on a logarithmic scale, Fig. 1. The majority of systems (perhaps 80%) fall into a broad, log-normal peak centred at $\Delta(\text{rel}) = 15$ mas and with a s.d. of about 0.4 dex. Then there are narrow peaks at one and two grid periods (~ 1250 and 2500 mas), plus some scattered points in the 150–600 mas interval.

The whole material (2634 systems) was divided according to $\Delta(\text{rel})$ and the differences in absolute position, parallax and proper motion were calculated for each interval. The differences are defined as:

$$\Delta(\text{pos}) = (\Delta\alpha^2 + \Delta\delta^2)^{0.5} \quad (5)$$

$$\Delta(\text{par}) = |\pi_N - \pi_F| \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta(\text{pm}) = (\Delta\mu_\alpha^2 + \Delta\mu_\delta^2)^{0.5} \quad (7)$$

where $\Delta\alpha = (\alpha_N - \alpha_F) \cos \delta$, $\Delta\delta = \delta_N - \delta_F$, and $\Delta\mu_\alpha$, $\Delta\mu_\delta$ the corresponding differences in p.m. The median values of $\Delta(\text{pos})$, $\Delta(\text{par})$ and $\Delta(\text{pm})$ are plotted in Fig. 2 versus $\Delta(\text{rel})$. There is a relatively clear limit at $\Delta(\text{rel}) = 70$ mas, beyond which the differences in the absolute astrometry starts to grow. Consequently subsequent studies were limited to the 1865 systems with $\Delta(\text{rel}) \leq 70$ mas.

[Actually the absolute parameters often agree very well also for the systems with $\Delta(\text{rel})$ about 1250 and 2500 mas, but for simplicity they were not considered in the following.]

4. NDAC-FAST differences in absolute astrometry

The values of $\Delta(\text{pos})$, $\Delta(\text{par})$ and $\Delta(\text{pm})$ were analyzed as function of separation (ρ) and magnitude difference (Δm) for the 1865 systems with $\Delta(\text{rel}) \leq 70$ mas.

Figure 3 shows the median differences plotted against ρ on logarithmic scales. It is noted that the behaviour of $\Delta(\text{pos})$ is markedly different from that of $\Delta(\text{par})$ and $\Delta(\text{pm})$. The latter two quantities are roughly independent of ρ , or perhaps they increase slightly from the closest to the most separated pairs. For $\Delta(\text{pos})$ the same can be said only for the well-separated pairs ($\rho > 500$ mas), while for the close pairs the positional differences are considerably higher. Typical values are (at intermediate $\rho \sim 1000$ mas):

$$\text{median } \Delta(\text{pos}) = 4.0 \text{ mas}$$

$$\text{median } \Delta(\text{par}) = 2.5 \text{ mas}$$

$$\text{median } \Delta(\text{pm}) = 7.6 \text{ mas/yr.}$$

The increase in $\Delta(\text{pos})$ for small separations indicates that part of the spread in the primary positions is caused by the difficulty to estimate the separation of the primary from the photocentre. This can be tested more directly by computing the quantity $\Delta(\text{pc})$, analogous to (5) but referring to the photocentre (pc) rather than the primary. Figure 4 shows the median $\Delta(\text{pc})$ versus ρ . For $\rho < 400$ mas (approximately) the position of the photocentre is more consistently estimated than the primary position, whereas for wider separations the primary position should be preferred. (In the context of the light modulation by the grid the photocentre has no special significance for $\rho > 400$ mas.) For close binaries ($\rho < 300$ mas) the agreement in the photocentric positions is much better:

$$\text{median } \Delta(\text{pc}) = 2.9 \text{ mas.}$$

Figure 5 shows the median $\Delta(\text{pos})$, $\Delta(\text{par})$ and $\Delta(\text{pm})$ versus the magnitude difference. As could be expected, the FAST-NDAC differences are worst for small Δm and improve with increasing magnitude difference. For binaries which are, effectively, almost single ($\Delta m > 3$), typical levels are:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{median } \Delta(\text{pos}) &= 2.3 \text{ mas} \\ \text{median } \Delta(\text{par}) &= 1.7 \text{ mas} \\ \text{median } \Delta(\text{pm}) &= 5.0 \text{ mas/yr.} \end{aligned}$$

It is interesting to compare these numbers with the corresponding numbers for the 18 months sphere comparison. For large Δm one would hope that the absolute double star astrometry should not be as accurate as the single star astrometry. For the single stars we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{median } \Delta(\text{pos}) &= 1.53 \text{ mas} \\ \text{median } \Delta(\text{par}) &= 1.17 \text{ mas} \\ \text{median } \Delta(\text{pm}) &= 3.48 \text{ mas/yr.} \end{aligned}$$

The double star astrometry thus consistently gives 40-50% higher differences.

Clearly it would be desirable to divide the material simultaneously in ρ and Δm , but the number of systems is too small to provide much useful statistics.

5. Comparison with sphere solution

Of the 1865 systems analyzed above, 373 also had (single-star) data in the NDAC 30 months solution (run #204). I have looked separately at the FAST-SPH and NDAC-SPH differences. It should be recalled that the NDAC double-star analysis is much more decoupled from the single-star analysis than is the case in FAST, so the comparison is not as unfair as it may seem at first glance.

Figure 6 shows the position differences FAST-SPH (top) and NDAC-SPH (bottom) versus ρ . These diagrams are for the primary positions. The dashed lines are $\Delta(\text{pos}) = 0.5\rho$: as one would expect, the positional error very seldom exceeds half the separation. Also, as expected, the 'worst' agreement with the sphere is found for a separation of 400-500 mas (and presumably small Δm).

Figure 7 is the corresponding diagram for the photocentric positions. The best agreement is of course found for close binaries; e.g., for $\rho < 250$ mas the median difference is 3.7 mas for the FAST data and 2.0 mas for NDAC. It can be noted that $\Delta(\text{pc})$ is proportional to the cube of the separation up to $\rho \simeq 500$ mas, after which the exponent is about 0.8.

Figure 8 shows the parallax differences versus ρ . No particular trend is seen in the mean value or in the scatter. The median absolute difference is 1.8 mas for FAST and 1.2 mas for NDAC.

Figure 9 shows the proper motion differences versus ρ . The median difference is about 6.9 mas/yr for FAST and 3.8 mas/yr for NDAC, rather independent of separation.

In Figure 10 the parallax differences are plotted against the p.m. differences. It is seen that a proper motion difference w.r.t. the sphere of more than about 30 mas/yr is usually accompanied by a large difference in the parallaxes. This is not unexpected, but emphasises that the large differences in both parameters are concentrated to the same subset of about 10% of the 373 stars in this sample. Taking a limit of 30 mas/yr in p.m. and 20 mas in parallax there are 37 such stars which I have examined more closely to see if they have some particular feature in common that could explain the large differences w.r.t. the sphere. About a third of them have large formal errors, but otherwise they appear to be quite representative in terms of ρ and Δm .

Figure 11 shows the differences in parallax versus Δm . The lines indicate the 1st and 5th sextiles, which roughly correspond to ± 1 s.d. Note that the intersextile width increases towards small Δm for the FAST data, but not for the NDAC data. For large Δm the width is about the same for FAST and NDAC.

Figure 12 shows the proper motion differences versus Δm . The line indicates the median. This is practically independent of Δm for NDAC, but increases towards the small magnitude differences in the FAST data.

6. Distributions of parallaxes and proper motions

The comparisons with the NDAC sphere in the previous section all point in the direction that the FAST absolute astrometry is generally less accurate than the corresponding NDAC data. This conclusion might be biased by the circumstance that the double star data could only be compared with the NDAC sphere solution (none of these stars appear in the FAST sphere solutions).

A more objective impression of the relative quality of the FAST and NDAC data is obtained by plotting the distributions of the actual parallax and proper motion values for the 1865 systems with $\Delta(\text{rel}) \leq 70$ mas (Fig. 13 and 14). The parallax histograms clearly demonstrate that the NDAC values are more accurate. The proper motion diagrams lead to the same conclusion, although the difference is not so obvious here.

7. Formal errors

The comparison files also contain the formal standard errors of all five astrometric parameters and the ten correlations. These are data which I have only looked at very superficially. One thing is worth noting, however. The formal errors of the parallaxes and proper motions are compared in Fig. 15. The distribution is much wider for FAST than for NDAC. The fairly complicated weight manipulation done in NDAC probably prevents the formal errors from becoming smaller than about 1 mas. Also, there may be a selection against systems with large formal errors. These two factors may explain the more confined NDAC distribution. In the FAST data there are many data with extremely small formal errors — a few tenths of a

mas, even 0.0 mas for some stars (as the data are rounded to one decimal) — but also a lot of very large formal errors (up to 200 mas in the parallaxes!), which should rather have been rejected.

8. Conclusions

The results of the present comparison are a bit more encouraging than the first report (DSWG.LO.001). However, the agreement between FAST and NDAC is still considerably worse for the double stars than for single stars. Even for large Δm , where one expects to approach the single-star situation, the differences are 40–50% larger than for single stars. For very small Δm the disagreement is another factor 10 larger. It is difficult to decide exactly where the problem is, but comparisons with the sphere results hint at some difficulty with small Δm in the FAST solutions. Apparently, the FAST results are in general less accurate.

FAST should also consider how to obtain more realistic formal standard errors to their solutions — or rather the weighting of the input data should be revised. Perhaps part of the problem could be related to erroneous relative weights of the different observations of the same object.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

Figure 9.

Figure 10.

Figure 11.

Figure 12.

Figure 13.

Figure 14.

Figure 15.